

EXPERIENCES AND SENSES AN EXPERIMENTAL BASED METHODOLOGY FOR THE DESIGN OPTIMIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Understanding users' points of view is rapidly becoming an urgent issue for companies and designers, as well as User Experience and Experience Design proving to be of wide interest for academic research. This paper presents an experimental-based methodology aimed at guiding designers during product optimisation. It is meant to support designers in choosing the right strategy to assess the users' emotional reaction towards a product at an early stage of product development. The methodology consists of three different phases: 1) Design Challenge definition, to help in clarifying the research question; 2) Interaction Study, aimed at understanding the user experience; 3) Sensory Boost phase, to improve the products perceived pleasurableness. The methodology includes a review of the methods and tools used for catching users' emotional reactions to products. Moreover, a computer-based version of the methodology will be introduced, together with two case studies to validate the developed methodology.

KEYWORDS: *Emotional Design, User Experience, Methodology, Sensory Boost.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's market world, differentiating products from competitors' is a fundamental matter for industries that want to stand up and gain the preference of consumers (Spence and Gallace 2011). In order to differentiate their offers, producers reached closer to the consumer preferences, by developing products studied not only to provide better usability and interaction, but also to elicit positive emotional reactions in the consumer (Khalid and Helander, 2006). In the design and consumer research, importance of both pragmatic and hedonic-emotional aspects of the products has been theorized and supported by several authors, particularly fitting into the concept of experience design (Shedroff, 2001). The present paper introduces a methodology to support designers in the optimization of the product from an experience design perspective. It consists in a collection of experimental methods aiming at gathering information from the user, thus providing the designer with the data necessary to augment his/her understanding of the consumer's experience.

The methodology in the User Experience Design framework

Since Donald Norman's seminal works (Norman, 2002), the importance of users' emotions and personal needs in the design process has been considered as a crucial point in product design. This view has evolved nowadays into the core principles of User Experience Design (UXD). UXD plays on the emotional and personal needs of the users, placing as much attention as it does on the usability and practical matters, trying to account for the entire experience by involving the users (Shedroff, 2001). According to Forlizzi and Battarbee (2004), designers can consider the experience from a number of perspectives, which have been grouped by the authors into three main categories: *product-centered*, *user-centered*, and *interaction-centered*.

The proposed methodology adopts a conception of experience design from a user-centered perspective (Hassenzahl, 2003, 2008). According to this view, users perceive products according to two main dimensions: pragmatic and hedonic. Pragmatic qualities of a product refer to its ability in accomplishing 'do-goals', which are the purposes for which the object has been created for (for example, a do-goal for a pen is 'write'). Hedonic qualities refer instead to the product's per-

ceived ability to support the achievement of ‘be-goals’. Be-goals represent the hedonic and symbolic needs of the user (referring to the example of the pen, a be-goal for an elegant-shaped pen could be to ‘be professional’, or ‘be elegant’).

In this view, then, the interaction with the product is achieved through the product’s pragmatic and hedonic qualities. Users, in fact, perceive those qualities through their senses. The interaction itself is a motor act allowed by the perception of the features composing the design of the object. In a psychological view, the hedonic features of the object are perceived by senses, and interpreted as being able to satisfy the needs of the user. In the same way, the pragmatic features of the object, that allow the user to use the product for its material purpose, are connected to the user sensory perception. To be usable, a product must match all the sensorial needs of the user, providing all the sensory feedback in the fashion necessary to optimize the accomplishment of the task it has been created for. As an example, it would be pointless creating an alarm not perceivable by the user; the sound of the alarm is needed to recall the user’s attention and to trigger an action.

According to this, our methodology constitutes a procedure, based on experimental methods, which can support designers aiming at augmenting the efficacy of the sensorial feedback underpinning the hedonic and pragmatic features of the product. Indeed, the final goal is to provide the designer with information concerning how the product is perceived and how the sensory characteristics of the product are elaborated by the user brain. This will facilitate the product optimization, thus obtaining a more usable and, eventually, more emotional design.

Experimental based approaches for product design optimization

Over the years, a series of studies have been conducted in the design and marketing fields in order to highlight how to guide the designers in understanding the users’ perception of the product, and therefore spotting the user preferences and implementing them in the design solution. For example, Raz et al. (2008) set up a protocol aiming to act on the sensorial characteristic of the product, based on experimental data collected from consumers. Similar methodologies have been proposed for years in the realm of design of food products and aliments. Ellekjaer et al. (1996) studied a strategy aimed to improve the sensory qualities of a food product, based on

a sensory description of the product followed by multivariate statistical analysis, and a different strategy used to link the user perception of the product with the design solution was reported by Buchenau and Suri (2000). The method, rooted in the co-design realm, involved an active collaboration between users and designers at the prototyping phase.

In 2009 Kaczorowska made the effort of listing a series of methods used nowadays to relate the consumer perception to the product development (Kaczorowska, 2011). He organized the methods according to their appearance in five different phases of the design process: idea generation, concept generation, prototype development, verifying test, and product introduction to marketing. In addition, in order to verify the final solution, Kaczorowska suggested the use of boredom test, preference test, and finally purchase intent test. In the fifth phase, which is the introduction of the product in the market, no method is described.

However, despite the attention that these methods have on the user perception and to his (her) reactions to the product, they do not explicitly fit into the experience design realm. More specifically, in all the cases, when a method investigates the hedonic dimension of a product, it usually ignores the pragmatic one, and vice versa. In this paper we introduce a methodology, which aims to help designers in optimizing their products, providing tools to explore the users’ perception of the product under both the pragmatic and hedonic point of view.

THE METHODOLOGY: A THREE-PHASE PROCESS FOR THE PRODUCT DESIGN OPTIMIZATION

The methodology proposed is composed by three different phases: The Design Question phase, the Interaction Study, and finally the *Sensory Boost* (Figure 1).

In particular, during the first phase the designer highlights and makes clear the design question expressed by the client (marketing experts, customers, etc.). In the second stage, the interaction between user and product is assessed, in order to find the important characteristics of the product that are related to the design question. Finally, a sensory optimization experiment is performed in order to optimize the product by means of cross modal correspondences or threshold measurements.

Figure 1: the methodology

Figure 2: a screenshot of the computer-based version

According to the methodology presented in this paper, a computer-based framework has been developed. In particular, designers interacting with the computer-based framework are presented with information on each stage of the methodology. This information is aimed to help the designer in focusing on the right design question (phase one), in choosing the right method for the user-product interaction (phase two), and in performing the sensory boost (phase three). It is important to note, however, that the designer will be left free to perform all the design choices within each phase, and no preferential way to go through the different steps of the methodology will be provided. (Figure two).

Definition of the design question

The first phase of the methodology can be considered as a preliminary phase, and it is related to the design question to which the designer wishes to answer. Does the client want a more efficacious product? A more usable one? Does the client want to communicate feelings with the object he (she) is going to re-create?

Although it may seem easy, there are many issues that should draw the attention of the designer in clarifying the design question posed by the client. A better understanding of the challenge may reduce the risks of choosing the wrong strategy of experiments, thus allowing for the setting up of the user tests in a more accurate way. In this manner, the designer will be able to focus only on what the customer effectively needs to understand in order to improve the product experience. However, it is not always easy to understand what the client

wants, and often the client cannot be aware of the direction the design process has to take.

As a matter of fact, a first step is to understand, referring to the experience design framework, whether the changes of the product belong to its pragmatic or hedonic characteristics (or even both). Concerning the hedonic characteristic of the product, a guide to better structure the design question can be found in the needs the user wants to satisfy. Sheldon and colleagues (Sheldon et al., 2001) compared ten candidates' psychological needs in an attempt to determine which were truly fundamental for users. They found that autonomy, competence, and relatedness, were consistently among the top four needs, in terms of both their salience and their association with event-related affect. Self-esteem was also important, whereas self-actualization or meaning, physical thriving, popularity or influence, and money-luxury were less important, but still present. It is advisable then, in the optimization, to look at how a given product is able to satisfy these needs, in order to re-define the design question.

At the same time, it could be crucial in the pragmatic optimization to understand whether the user would actually benefit by an augment of the product's performance, either augmenting the user perception of the performance of the product, or keeping the performance of the product constant while diminishing the costs. As a matter of fact, in some cases the designer cannot improve the performance of the product because this would exceed his or her competences. In other cases though, a design aid is useful and even necessary. In these cases a pragmatic optimization would be of great use.

Figure 3 the panel in the computer-based version of the methodology, where the designer is allowed to look through the most appropriate methods by applying some selection filters

Interaction Studies

Once the design question is defined, the second phase of the methodology deals with gathering information on the interaction between user and product by means of the application of experimental methods. The final aim of this stage is to point out which product features are considered important by the user in addressing the design question, so as to subsequently (during the third phase) boost these features. It is important to note that the methodology is not restrictive on which methods to use to relate user and product, as far as this relationship is investigated. The computer-based version of the product currently includes a list of eighteen methods (Figure three), each of them described and explained by means of examples and scientific references.

Moreover, in the computer-based version, a number of filters are available to help the designer in selecting the best experimental methods according to his/her needs and skills. In particular, the filters are: the affordable number of participants, the level of complexity of the experiment (which includes equipment, phases, set up, prototypes, etc.), the supposed skills in analysing data (some of the tools may require high statistical skills), the contribution the experiment brings in addressing a pragmatic question, the contribution the experiment brings in addressing a hedonic question, and a further categorisation of the methods and tools, explicit or implicit. In fact, explicit experiments include an explicit assessment of the participants on the tested object, while implicit experiments do not necessarily ask the participant for feedback on the interaction itself.

The explicit experiments so far included in the computer-based version of the methodology are:

- Questionnaires (i.e., Gentile, Spiller, Noci, 2007).
- Written analysis (i.e., Fenko, Schifferstein, and Hekkert, 2010).
- Cards sorting (i.e., Chen and Occena, 1999).
- Attrakdiff (i.e., Hassenzhal, Burmester, Koller, 2003).
- Sensory snapshot (i.e., Moskovitz, 2004).
- Quality function deployment (i.e., Costa, Dekker, and Jongen, 2000).
- Product Emotion Measurement instrument (PrEmo) (i.e., Desmet, Hekkert, and Jacobs, 2000).
- Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) (Bradley and Lang, 1985).
- Emotion wheel (Sacharin, Schlegel, and Scherer 2012).

Among them, a specific role is covered by the methods applying multivariate statistics to the data, such as Multi-Dimensional Scaling, and the final stages of Conjoint Analysis and Semantic Differentials Method. These methods deserve a separate classification because, despite the fact they ask direct assessment about the product, they also provide further implicit information about how consumers interpret and categorize the products. The methods based on multivariate analysis included in the computer-based methodology are:

- Conjoint Analysis. (i.e., Moskowitz et al., 2005).
- Multi-Dimensional Scaling (MDS) for the perceptual space (i.e., Giboreau et al., 2001).

- Semantic Differentials Method (SDM) (i.e., Osgood et al., 1957).
- Kansei engineering (Nagamachi, 2008).

Instead, the implicit experiments so far treated by the methodology are:

- Eye tracking. (i.e., Piqueras-Fiszman et al., 2012).
- Body tracking. (i.e., Bianchi-Berthouze et al., 2006)
- Implicit Association Test (IAT). (i.e., Parise and Spence, 2012).
- Evaluation of the physiological activation. (i.e., Picard, 2003).
- Neural activations (i.e., Picard, 2003).

The second phase of the methodology offers a comprehensive review of tools, but it is still far from being exhaustive of all the experimental methods adopted during the years to study products' perception. It is, in fact, a starting point. Further methods will be implemented in the future.

Sensory Boost

The last phase actually represents the core of the methodology. In fact, most of the works on design optimization stop after achieving information from the methods listed in the interaction phase. It is theoretically possible to improve a product without going through the sensory boost phase. For example, obtaining an optimized product would be possible after conjoint analysis or QFD. Unfortunately, however, these improvements often lead to trade-offs between the features to improve (and/or to add), the price of the product (which usually rises), and other features that might be related with the original setting of the product (Green & Srinivasan, 1978; Zarei et al., 2011).

Let us imagine, for example, that the users' preference for a cell-phone or a tablet is driven by the luminosity of the screen. The brighter the screen, the more the users like the product. Let us then suppose that for each Watt of luminosity the battery of the tablet lasts for a little less time, which is obviously not convenient nor appreciated by the user. In this case, a trade off analysis is usually performed, in order to maximize the benefit of adding luminosity and minimize the drawback of losing battery autonomy. However, it seems legitimate to ask: Is this trade-off that necessary? In the field of sensory science, it is well known that there is a relationship between background and perceived brightness (e.g. Cohen & Grossberg, 1984). It would therefore likely be possible, then, that instead of performing a trade-off on the tablet, the color or the size of the frame of the screen could be changed, so as to augment its perceived brightness without influencing the battery's performance and endurance.

The aim of the sensory boost is, indeed, to assess these kinds of optimization, retrieving information concerning users' sensory perception of the important product features, trying to enhance them in a perceptive way. According to the methodology outlined here, two main ways of investigating users'

perception are the study of crossmodal correspondences and the use of psychophysical methods. Whereas crossmodal correspondences are suitable for both a pragmatic and a hedonic optimization, suggesting semantic and experiential concepts to the consumers, the psychophysics is basically the discipline that measures the ability of humans to perceive given feedback, and therefore is particularly suited for the pragmatic optimization.

Crossmodal correspondences

The study of how multisensory information is coded by our brains has widely interested researchers in sensory science for many years now (Calvert et al., 2004). Interestingly, a new research trend focused on what are called crossmodal correspondences is now emerging.

The term 'crossmodal correspondence' includes a range of topics expressed in literature under different names (i.e., 'synesthetic correspondences', and 'synesthetic associations' — just to name a few). In fact, crossmodal correspondences, '...refer to a compatibility effect between attributes or dimensions of a stimulus (i.e.: an object or event) in different sensory modalities (be they redundant or not)' (Spence, 2011).

Crossmodal correspondences have often been studied by means of relatively simple mappings (or associations) between stimuli presented in modalities such as vision and audition (i.e., Marks, 2003); vision and olfaction (i.e., Demattè et al., 2006; Maric & Jacquot, 2013); touch and olfaction (i.e., Demattè et al., 2006) etc.

Crossmodal correspondences found also a large application to product design (Spence, 2012). As is not difficult to imagine, it is a thrilling concept for a designer to suggest sensation, or ideas to the consumer, by means of 'mere' sensory stimulation. In some extent, crossmodal correspondence represents everything that design is about, and what the design shares with art: to express your own aesthetic sense and elicit in the consumer, by means of a sensoria experience, concepts and ideas. More recently, crossmodal correspondences have been applied to product design assessing their effect by means of experiments (see Schifferstein & Spence, 2007, for a review), and the effect of the packaging on the perception of the product itself (see Spence & Piqueras-Fiszman, 2012; Piqueras-Fiszman et al., 2013, for a review).

For example, Piqueras-Fiszman and Spence (2012a) recently investigated the influence that the weight of food containers, cutlery, and packaging has on feelings of satiety (before and after tasting the food, in their case, a yogurt), and/or on the perception of density of the food itself. These researchers reported that increasing the weight (of the packaging/plate ware/cutlery) influenced the perceived density of the product contained inside (see Spence & Piqueras-Fiszman, 2012b, for a review). These researchers also confirmed the weight-density illusion originally proposed by Piqueras-Fiszman et al. (2011). The participants in this study also expected the contents of a heavier container to be more satiating than when exactly the same contents were presented in a visually-

identical, but physically lighter, container. A number of other studies have focused on investigating the visual features of products and their containers. The appearance of the product and the colour of its packaging also exert a significant influence on consumer perception, behaviour, and preferences (i.e., Marshall et al., 2006).

In fact, studies in crossmodal correspondences are versatile and applicable both to the pragmatic and hedonic characteristics of the product. However, all the studies on crossmodal correspondences have been carried out basing on the intuition of designers and psychologists rather than following a systematic methodology able to spot which aspect of the product to enhance or optimize utilizing this sensory science. This methodology is able to direct the studies on the sensory characteristics of the product onto the important features of the product itself, in order to enhance both its pragmatic and hedonic characteristics.

Psychophysics

Psychophysics has been used for many years in order to test the resolution of our perceptual systems (in particular, hearing, haptics, and vision). For decades the main objective of psychophysics has been the establishment of perceptual thresholds that could describe the sensitivity of our sensory systems under different conditions (Purghé, 1997). In particular, psychophysics focuses on the definition of absolute limen (AL), and differential limen (DL). AL is defined as the minimum level of stimulation needed to elicit a sensation in a person. DL instead refers to the minimum difference needed to be presented to the person for them to be able to distinguish between two stimuli of the same kind that appear to vary in intensity. Another main objective of psychophysics is the creation of scales regarding human sensations. Characteristic of such scales is the fact that they connect a given physical variable to a sensoria or psychological variable.

As a matter of fact, psychophysics assumes a great importance when it comes to assess the pragmatic characteristics of the design product. Especially in cases such as interface and new technology device design, it is important for the designer to be sure that all the feedback is clearly perceivable by the users. On the other hand it might be useful for the designer to know the limits of the human perception, in order to avoid wasting effort and time in designing oversensitive devices (see Gallace & Spence, 2014).

According to classic psychophysics, there are different methods to assess AL and DL. In particular, in the computer-based version of the methodology, some of the principal methods are described, and the experimental procedure to investigate thresholds and the formulas to compute them are enlisted. In particular, the methods of limits, adjustments, and constant stimuli are exposed.

Psychophysics has been used to validate or obtain information that can guide the design of devices and interfaces (i.e., Tan, Durlach, Reed, & Rabinowitz, 1999). Furthermore, in these cases, the performed studies were isolated, rather than framed as

part of a design methodology. The use of psychophysics in the methodology presented here is instead well defined. Thanks to the Interaction Study phase, the designer can find which kinds of sensorial feedback the user pays more attention to, and under which condition the user will need to perceive them. Subsequently, the threshold measures will serve as concrete guidelines to design/optimize that feedback.

CASE STUDY

Several case studies have been developed using the methodology reported above. In the following section, a case study will be exposed as an example to illustrate the efficacy and the functioning of the present methodology. More specifically, in the present case study, the design question was related to the concept of efficacy, and in particular asked how to augment the perceived expected efficacy of a liquid soap at the moment of purchase. It is important to note that the same case study could serve as an example also for a hedonic optimization procedure as well. In fact, the procedure would not change with a different design question (i.e., how to augment the perceived pleasantness of the product). In the case study outlined, we performed a Conjoint Analysis experiment in order to find out the sensory attributes related to the idea of efficacy in the liquid soap. We subsequently performed an experiment to boost the perceived efficacy of the soap by means of crossmodal correspondences.

Design question: In this case the design question we were asked to answer was: How to augment the perceived expected efficacy of the product when the user has to choose it from the shelves of a supermarket? In order to answer to this question we first performed a screening of the literature on crossmodal correspondence applied to hygiene, body care, and bath product, focusing specifically on soaps and body lotions finding, as reported in the literature (i.e., Churchill et al., 2009), that the role of olfaction in product evaluation was crucial.

Interaction study: In the second phase, in order to study the perception of the user in terms of efficacy, a conjoint analysis experiment was performed on twenty healthy participants (twelve male), aged between nineteen and thirty-four years (mean of twenty-six years). A set of twelve identical soap bottles (Figure four) were painted in one of three different colors: white (low color intensity), pink (medium color intensity), and red (high color intensity). Two different quantities of perfume were added to the soaps contained in the bottles. The lower concentration consisted of three drops of a strong perfume essence ('Dragon's Blood'), whereas the higher concentration consisted of the addition of seven drops per bottle. The essence was thoroughly mixed with the soap in the bottle, and the weight of half the bottles was increased by inserting a 100-gram weight into the soap container. The task of the participant was to interact with each bottle (lifting it, smelling the content, etc.), and subsequently rate the expected efficacy of each bottle of soap using a Borg CR100 response scale (Borg, 2007).

Figure 4: Stimuli used in the case study

An Analysis Of Variance (ANOVA), that included weight, fragrance, and color as predictors was applied to the data. According to this analysis, the soap contained in the heavier bottles was rated as having a higher expected efficacy ($p < .01$). Moreover, although there was not a significant effect of bottle color saturation, or fragrance intensity on perceived efficacy, the mean expected efficacy for the bottles with the lower fragrance intensity was lower than that for the bottles with the higher fragrance intensity, and the p value concerning that factor was relatively low. Therefore, the factors to consider relevant when the user had to judge the expected efficacy of a product were considered to be fragrance intensity and weight. Therefore the third phase of the optimization procedure was applied.

Sensory boost: In this phase a sensory experiment was performed, in order to exploit the phenomenon of crossmodal correspondences augmenting the perceived weight and the perceived fragrance of the bottle's contents using sensory signals coming from different sensory channels. The senses of taste and hearing were not considered, since it is unlikely that these two senses could be used in a market-like environment. For this study, the same stimuli and procedure of the conjoint analysis were used. Participants were asked to rate with the same modality the Borg CR100 scale, but this time on the perceived intensity of the fragrance. Moreover, participants were also asked to give an estimation of the weight of each bottle.

To test for any effects of color, fragrance intensity, and product weight on the perceived intensity of the liquid soap contained within the bottles, an analysis of variance (ANOVA; $\alpha = 0.05$) was performed on the data ($p < .001$). Post-hoc comparison (Bonferroni corrected: $\alpha = .05/3$) revealed statistically significant differences in the perceived intensity of the fragrance of the soap, as a function of the color of the bottle (all p s $< .001$).

In particular, the liquid soap presented in the red bottles was perceived (on average) as having a fragrance that was significantly stronger than that of the other bottles. That is, the participants rated the fragrance sniffed from red bottles as being 16% more intense than the fragrance sniffed from the pink bottles, and as being 44% more intense than the fragrance sniffed from the white bottles. Meanwhile, the fragrance of

the soap contained in the pink bottles was rated as 30% more intense than the perfume of the soap contained in the white bottles. As expected, the bottles containing the more intense fragrance were rated as having a smell that was 30% stronger than the bottles containing the weaker fragrance ($p < .001$). Interestingly, the liquid soap contained in the heavier bottles was also rated, on average, as having a fragrance that was 15% more intense than the soap contained in the lighter bottles ($p < .05$). No statistically significant effects of the interactions between the considered factors were observed.

An ANOVA ($\alpha = 0.05$) was also performed in order to test for the effects of color, fragrance intensity, and weight on the perceived weight of the bottles. No effect of the other sensory modalities was found on the estimated weight. Indeed, the only effect that was documented related to the weight inserted into the bottles.

Conclusion: In the present case study the ability to enhance the expected efficacy of liquid bath soap was examined and augmented by means of the proposed methodology. In the interaction phase of the study, the characteristics of the product important in determining its expected efficacy (that were: fragrance and weight) were highlighted. Subsequently, a sensory study was performed on fragrance and weight, in order to boost these two characteristics of the product by means of crossmodal correspondences. Results reported that changing the color of the bottles and augmenting their weight would augment the perceived fragrance, and as a consequence the perceived efficacy of the product. In fact by only acting on the packaging, without modifying the content of the bottle, designers would be able to reach an optimized product.

CONCLUSIONS

The present work exposes a methodology aimed at supporting designers in enhancing the product experience by means of experimental methods. In particular the methodology comprises a first phase in which the designer clarifies the design question expressed by the client. In a second stage, the interaction between user and product is assessed, adopting one or more experimental tools, which are reviewed in the computer-based version. In this way, the designer will understand the product's most important characteristics related to the design question. Finally, a sensory optimization experiment is performed in order to enhance and improve the product experience by means of cross modal correspondences or threshold measurements. A case study is also provided to show how the methodology works in practice.

A further aim of this methodology can be seen as to understand, revise, and finally expose methods and theories connected with the last two phases, in order to allow the designer to choose the methods to apply during the design process. Eighteen methods have been already listed in the Interaction Study section, plus three methods that have been inserted into the psychophysical phase.

It is noteworthy that both the second and third phases of the methodology require basic statistical skills. However, it is common for the designer to work in a multidisciplinary environment, where information from the market is often considered and analyzed by means of statistical tests. We assume therefore that it is not hard nowadays for a designer to deal with statistical data and results, maybe while asking for a little help. Moreover, the statistical skills required by the majority of the methods are basic, and there are plenty of computer programs able to perform them in a semi-automatic way.

Further objectives see the computer-based version of the methodology made available online, and editable by whoever is willing to add a new method or useful information to it.

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